

"Teacher and Students' Communication Patterns in Improving Learning Motivation During the Covid-19 Pandemic (A Study At Smp Negeri 6 Ternate, Indonesia)"

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ABSTRACT: *The Covid-19 pandemic that hit Indonesia also had an impact on the education system, forcing the government to impose new habits, rules, and decisions that had never been implemented in the education sector. The education system in Indonesia and many parts of the world is experiencing the same thing as a result of efforts to prevent the spread of the Covid-19 virus. Online learning is a process of distance learning methods using laptops and gadgets that allow teachers and students to interact or communicate well using communication and information media. This is done to reduce the amount of direct communication between teachers and students and to reduce crowds during the pandemic. There are many applications that can be used for online learning, such as: WhatsApp groups, google classroom, zoom meetings, and many other online applications. One of the schools that offers online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic is SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City. The communication involved in this research was teacher-student communication, and how teachers used good communication/relationship patterns between teachers and students during the pandemic to encourage students to learn. And the theory used was the theory of symbolic interaction. This study employed descriptive qualitative methods to describe or explain teacher communication patterns to motivate students at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate during the pandemic. The results showed that the communication pattern used by teachers to communicate with their students at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate is to use a linear communication pattern from communicator to communicant as an end point which is in accordance with its meaning. The communication process is usually face-to-face communication, but can also be displayed on communication media, and the learning process can be done online, offline, or face to face. It is based on the theory of symbolic interactionism, which emphasizes the role of communication in interpersonal relationships and the formation and leadership of social groups. Teachers as educators convey positive messages and symbols for the meaning of online and offline learning. This means that students will continue to study quietly using the opportunities and means of communication used in the learning process. Due to the pandemic situation, teachers also attached great importance to interpersonal relationships so that the intimacy between teachers and students remains psychologically friendly.*

KEYWORDS – *Teacher and Student Communication Patterns, Learning Motivation, Covid-19 Pandemic.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is like thinking between people as needed. Communication is not only the exchange of information and messages, but also the activities of individuals and groups exchanging data, facts, and ideas. According to **(William I. Gorden in Mulyana, 2005)**, the function of communication is also social communication. In short, communication is important for building self-concepts, self-actualization, survival, achieving happiness, and avoiding pressure, and nervous. When we communicate, we work together to achieve a common goal. The process of communication can take place anytime, anywhere, such as between parents and children in school, or between teachers and students in the context of education. During the Covid-19 pandemic that struck Indonesia, it also affected the education system, forcing the government to make rules and decisions in education, a new practice which has never been used before. Education in Indonesia and most parts of the world are experiencing the same due to efforts to prevent the spread of the Covid-19 virus.

This epidemic has made all forms of communication abnormal. This change in communication patterns also applies to the educational and learning processes used at both elementary and university levels throughout the world of education in Indonesia. This forced them to quit all personal activities, including training at their respective schools, like Ternate, specifically SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City. The change in teaching methods at school is an online learning model introduced by the government to reduce the number of people affected by the COVID 19 pandemic. Online learning is a learning through media equipped with network devices on the Internet.

Online learning is a method of distance learning using laptops and gadgets that allows teachers and students to interact with communication and information media, and to communicate well or interactively. This is done to reduce the amount of direct communication between teachers and students and to reduce the crowd during the pandemic. There are many applications that can be used for online learning, such as: WhatsApp Group, Google Classroom, E-learning, Zoom-Cloud, and Zoom-Meetings. The teachers at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City directed the education and learning activities at the school.

Communication between teachers and students must also be effective. This is to change the setting. The more people are involved in an effective communication process, the more it affects them and their behavior, because communication is basically the process of sending and receiving meaning or messages between communicators to achieve the same meaning and unity.

The communication referred to in this paper is teacher-student communication, a way for teachers to use good communication / relationship patterns between teachers and students to motivate students to learn during a pandemic. Communication built by the school during a pandemic like today with a well-developed communication pattern, with enthusiasm and encouragement to develop the right motivation from teachers by positioning students as a classroom goal.

Based on the background elaborated above, the author formulated the focus of the problem as: "In what extent do communication patterns of teachers at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate improve students' motivation during the Covid 19 pandemic?"

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

FORM OF COMMUNICATION

There are basically various forms of communication, such as interpersonal communication, group communication, and mass communication.

Intrapersonal communication is a communication process that occurs within a person. In other words, communication with yourself. In intrapersonal communication, people act as communicators **(Nofrin, 2018)**.

Interpersonal communication, also known as interpersonal communication, or face-to-face communication, allows each participant to directly absorb the reactions of others, both verbal and non-verbal. De Vito **(Liliweri, 1991)** explains that interpersonal communication sends messages received from others with direct intervention and feedback. Because this type of communication is a type of conversation, it is considered to be the most effective way in changing attitudes, behaviors, and attitudes. At the same time, stakeholders can feel the effects of interpersonal communication **(OSF, 2002)**. In the above definition, interpersonal communication refers to a form of communication in which two parties participate to achieve the same meaning. In addition, this form of communication can provide an opportunity to build good relationships with others. This communication is carried out by a group of people who interact to achieve a common goal, to know each other

and to see as part of the group (Mulyana, 2007). According to McLean, group communication is a dynamic process in which a small number of people participate in a conversation. Group communication is usually defined as involving 3 to 8 people. Large groups can be easily divided into several smaller groups (Ruliana & Lestari, 2019) Group communication has several characteristics. First, the process of communicating the message conveyed by the speaker to a more personal audience. Second, communication is continuous and can distinguish who is the source and who is the recipient. Third, the message conveyed is planned for a specific target audience segment and is not voluntary (**Nurdin, 2005**).

Organizational communication is communication that occurs within an organization, both formal and informal, and occurs through a larger network than group communication. Therefore, an organization can be interpreted as a group of groups. Formal communication includes organization-oriented and organization-based communication. This includes how you work in your company, your productivity, and the different types of work you need to do within your company (notes, guidelines, statements, press conferences, formal letters). Informal communication, on the other hand, belongs to communication recognized by the community. The orientation is intended for individual members of the organization itself (**DeVito, 2018**).

The media quoted by Jalaludin Rahmat, according to Elisabeth Noel Neumann, said: 1) Basically, it is done indirectly, that is, through the media of technology. 2) This is one-sided. That is, there is no interaction between communicators. 3) Open. That is, an unlimited number of people are treated. 4) Existence of a geographical audience (**Rachmat, 2005**).

Communication Pattern

Communication pattern is a form or pattern of relationship between two or more people in the process of sending and receiving in the right way so that the intended message can be understood (**Djamarah, 2004**). There are several types of communication patterns. Primary communication pattern is the process of using symbols as media or channels and transmitting them from communicator to communicator. This pattern is divided into two linguistic and non-linguistic symbols. Language symbols, or language, are used most often because language can express the communicator's ideas. Nonverbal symbols, on the other hand, are symbols used in communication, which are symbols that use body parts rather than language for examples, head, eyes, lips, hands, etc.

The secondary communication pattern is the process where the communicator uses symbols from the first medium and then sends them to the communicator using a tool or means as a second medium. Communicators who use this secondary medium for many communication purposes. This secondary communication process is more effective and efficient because it is supported by increasingly sophisticated information technology.

Linear communication patterns have a direct meaning. This means a linear movement from one point to another and means the delivery of the message through the communicator to the communicant as the end point. Therefore, this communication process is usually face-to-face communication, but can also be mediated communication. In this communication process, if you execute the plan before communicating, the message sent will be valid.

Circular communication patterns are defined as a circle or circumference. In the cyclical process, feedback, the flow from communicator to communicator, occurs as a major determinant of successful communication. In such a communication pattern, the communication process, namely the feedback between the communicators, continues. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the definition of a pattern is a system or way of working, a fixed form or arrangement in a game or government.

The focus of this research is SMP N 6 Ternate city. and the communication model used by teachers in teaching students in Ternate City. So this focus can be seen from the side. Are there primary communication patterns, secondary communication patterns, linear communication patterns, circular communication patterns.

Symbolic Interaction Theory

Symbolic interaction theory examines the nature of interaction, which is a dynamic human social activity. The theory of symbolic interaction is a typical human activity, namely the communication and exchange of symbols that are given meaning. The history of symbolic interactionism cannot be separated from the thinking of George Herbert Mead. Mead appears as a nonverbal or linguistic message conveyed by mutual consent by all participants in the interaction, and is seen in symbolic form. This has a very important meaning. A person's behavior is influenced by the symbols given by other people and their behavior. By sending signals in the form of symbols, you can express your feelings, thoughts, intentions, and vice versa by reading the symbols displayed by other people.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a qualitative descriptive survey method. According to **Moleong (2005)**, qualitative research aims to explain in words the overall phenomena experienced by research subjects, such as behavior, perception, motivation, and behavior. And in certain natural contexts, language uses different natural methods. This study described teacher's communication patterns to motivate students at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate during the pandemic. Descriptive studies aim to create a systematic, factual, and accurate picture of the facts and characteristics of a particular group or area (**Pujileksono, 2015**).

This research was conducted at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate, North Maluku. Primary data sources used as informants are divided into two parts. In summary, the main source of information for this study was the subject teachers of SMP Negeri 6 Ternate city, and secondary data were collected through books, reports, and research findings on the research problem.

The data acquisition technique used in this study was the observation at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate city, direct interviews with teachers, and documentation according to research needs. Data analysis techniques used in this study include data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, researchers focused on teacher-student communication patterns to provide learning motivation to students at SMP N 6 Ternate City during the Covid-19 pandemic. Communication in the context of interactions and transactions directly affected the process of exchanging information. Therefore, every pattern of communication processes requires good transmission and reception to achieve an effective communication effect. Communication in education is a very important factor and has a major impact on the success of education. Communication between teachers and students must also be effective. This is expected to change the attitudes and behavior of students in carrying out their educational process.

During the pandemic, school learning facilities are used to change the learning system that was previously face-to-face in front of the class. Now it is developing into online and offline learning which is carried out by schools through the Ministry of Education and carried out by Indonesian schools. Therefore, the communication process usually occurs in face-to-face communication, but it can also occur in mediated communication. Circular literally means circular, circular, or circular. In the cyclical process, feedback, the flow from communicator to communicator, occurs as a major determinant of successful communication. This study determines the focus of problem formulation on communication patterns to motivate learning during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The following are the results of interviews with teachers at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate with one research question as follows: Teacher Communication Patterns to students at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City in Improving student learning motivation during the Covid-19 pandemic. Based on the results of interviews with researchers with teachers of SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City. The following are the results of an interview with Mrs. Astuti Djumati, S.Pd, she explained that:

"During this pandemic, we as teachers of SMP N 6 Ternate City use the teaching and learning process in two ways, online and offline. Our online method uses the Zoom app, Whatsapp groups and Messenger. However, there are obstacles faced by teachers, students and parents during the learning process in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. This can be a problem, or online learning may not be optimal, such as complaints of insufficient android smartphone, lost data pulse, bad network, and so on. In addition to the online method, we also use the offline method where the teacher creates a portfolio for students to carry out the learning process independently or individually at home. After students study our portfolio, we go to students' homes to see and decide what they need to do. Through interpersonal communication with students and parents. In addition to online and offline learning methods, we also use mass media, namely Ternate Local Network Cable TV and Ternate RRI, as learning media for students. This method was initiated by the local government through the Ternate City Education Office. In this lesson, we don't know whether the students are listening or not."

During the pandemic, teachers conduct learning activities for students of SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City in two ways, namely online and offline. The media used were zoom applications and television mass media as learning media programmed by the Ternate City Education Office. The Ministry of Education provides educational content for each lesson through networked television media and broadcasts through networked television.

The following teacher agrees: Rugaya Balulu. , S.Pd., M.Si As Deputy Principal for Student Affairs, explained:

“The learning methods we use are online and offline, we use them online and we use the Zoom, Whatsapp and Messenger applications. The use of the app is unrestricted and each teacher is free to decide how to use it. Teachers can use several methods or as needed. The education and learning process is also hampered by communication devices and Android phones. Since some students do not have cell phones, we come directly from the school to their homes and provide them in portfolio form or with materials they have prepared. Modules while maintaining health protocols.”

Because teachers are role models for students, teachers always guarantee good learning, either directly or indirectly. Interactions carried out in the education and learning process carried out during the pandemic are certainly different because communication is built in direct and indirect forms. The method used is formal and informal with an interpersonal approach so that students do not feel uncomfortable or comfortable communicating with the teacher. The learning method used is different from the previous one, but there are many obstacles that students complain about. Students who participate in online learning can complete activities in addition to receiving materials.

All teachers want to learn well according to their goals and expectations. Achieving all of this requires an approach where students are more open and say what they need to do. In this way, all the expectations and goals that teachers and students want to achieve are fulfilled. And communication that is often used to motivate students to always learn with enthusiasm is intimate interpersonal communication. As the next teacher said.

Astuti Djumati, S.Pd said:

We, teachers, always provide motivational information and messages directly via messenger, whatsapp and telephone to establish communication with our students. This ensures that students are always able to complete the assignments through learning videos sent to students and assignments through portfolios. Occasionally, we communicate with the homeroom teacher who communicates the difficulties of the student's learning process and with the homeroom teacher who follows up to establish more focused communication with students. The effective communication patterns with students, in addition to face to face conversations, were also through WhatsApp.

Rugaya Balulu., S.Pd., M.Si, said teachers need to motivate students to learn. Teacher gives advice and stories about personal approach like family once a week and every two weeks. This allows students to always study individually and eager to solve problems solved at home. Sometimes, add humor when teaching with the Zoom app so students aren't nervous. Therefore, there is a flexible and relaxed learning environment.

From the results of interviews with several teachers, the average teacher's communication pattern is an interpersonal communication pattern that aims at intimacy and self-disclosure. Student self-assessment usually consists of saying what is needed to improve or motivate them to study independently in their homes. According to Skinner, in the learning theory approach, many behaviors change the environment and affect living things. According to Skinner, almost all identified human behavior is divided into two categories, namely respondent behavior, and operant behavior. The respondent's behavior is an unintentional act (reflex). For the respondent's behavior to act, stimuli occurred in the body are needed. Operant behavior is voluntary behavior that is conditioned differently from the respondent's behavior that occurs in response to certain stimuli. Operant conditioning is the process of reinforcing (positive or negative reinforcement) of operant behavior, which can be repeated or eliminated as desired. Skinner divided this reinforcement into two parts, namely positive reinforcement and negative reinforcement. Positive reinforcement as a stimulus can increase the occurrence of repetitive behavior, and negative reinforcement can reduce or eliminate behavior. Learning is a process of behavior change that is achieved because of learning through some new behavior improvement called operant conditioning. According to Skinner, the most important element of learning is meaningful improvement.

Learning theory first came from Winkel. According to him, learning is a mental or psychological activity that goes well in an active interaction environment. In addition, learning demands or leads to changes that are directly or indirectly attached to the person who does it. Learning changes the management of understanding in every aspect. Especially for children who are just starting to get to know each other. The learning process carried out during the pandemic certainly requires a good pattern in providing knowledge to teachers to students without forcing students to follow the learning process both online and offline. Adaptation is a major factor in the current learning process.

Based on the symbolic interaction theory approach according to La Rossan, where human-to-human interaction is described in this theory, interactions between individuals can develop self-concept, self-concept is human behavior, behavior, motivation is important for independent learning. The student's process is disturbed

by emotionally exhausting information, but students think positively and learn aggressively like a normal learning process.

In the explanation above, communication is the process of forming a self-concept, and in the interaction, there is the formation of messages, both verbal and nonverbal in the form of message meanings, signs, and actions. A meaning has no meaning as an understanding of the message sent by people from both parties or communication participants, unless it gets the same meaning for every word, phrase, or language code that exists, otherwise. Then can conclude the communication about the similarity of the meaning of the signs resulting from the interaction between the speaker and the listener. Therefore, symbolic interaction is a theory that emphasizes the role of communication in interpersonal relationships and the formation and management of social groups. Teachers as educators convey positive messages. This means that students will continue to study quietly using the opportunities and means of communication used in the learning process. Due to the pandemic situation, teachers also attach great importance to interpersonal relationships, so that the intimacy between teachers and students remains psychologically friendly.

George Herbert Mead explained that people are motivated to act on the meaning they give to other people, things, and events. This meaning comes from the language people use when communicating with others, in the context of interpersonal communication or in the realm of their personal thoughts. SMP Negeri 6 Kota Ternate enables teachers and students to achieve similar behavior.

The use of the communication pattern in this study was in accordance with the four communication patterns. From the explanation above, the researcher concludes that the communication pattern used by the teacher for student communication at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City is to use a communicator to communicant linear communication pattern as the end point that is in accordance with the meaning. In the communication process, it usually occurs in face-to-face communication, but it can also occur in communication media, and the learning process can be done online, offline or face to face.

V. CONCLUSION

Students at SMP Negeri 6 Ternate City hope to learn by continuously using positive stimuli with the aim of increasing the occurrence of positive behavior, providing good benefits, and avoiding negative behavior. Learning is a process of behavior change that is achieved as a result of learning through several new behavior improvements called operant conditioning. And communication is the process of forming self-concept, and in that interaction the meaning of messages, both verbal and nonverbal, is formed. Teachers as convey a positive message. This means that students will continue to study quietly and use the opportunities and communication tools used in the learning process. Due to the pandemic situation, teachers also prioritize interpersonal approaches, and the intimacy between teachers and students can continue to be felt without psychological distance.

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